

A Study of the Kinetics of the Inversion Process in Dilute Solutions of Sucrose in Presence of Hydrochloric Acid.

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Studies on the kinetics of the inversion of sucrose have generally been made with fairly concentrated solutions (generally with ten per cent. and more and in a few cases with five per cent. solutions). The investigations of Lewis and collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1120; *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1613) and Scatchard (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 2357; *ibid.*, 1923, 45, 1580) show that the mechanism of the inversion process is a highly complicated one and the presence of large amounts of cane sugar in the reaction mixtures increases the complexities of the problem. It occurred to us that a study of the course of inversion in very dilute solutions of sucrose might lead to a better understanding of the problem and the present investigation was accordingly undertaken.

We have adopted a purely chemical method for the estimation of invert sugar in the reaction mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL.

All the chemicals employed in the present investigation were of the highest grade purity, either Merck's or Kahlbaum's guaranteed analytical reagents. The specimen of cane sugar used was Merck's preparation for the determination of heat of combustion. The purity of this was tested polarimetrically before use and found perfectly satisfactory.

Most of the velocity measurements were carried out at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$ and a few at $45^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$, in an electrically regulated thermostat.

Conductivity water from a Hartley's still was used for the preparation of all the solutions.

Estimation of invert sugar.—It is well known that the amount of sucrose present along with reducing sugars greatly influences the extent to which Fehling's solution is reduced, thus introducing error in the estimation of any reducing sugar. It is also known that no

such error creeps in, if the total amount of sugar (reducing sugar + sucrose) taken for each assay does not exceed 100 milligrams (Quisumbing and Thomas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1521).

We have adopted in this investigation, for the estimation of invert sugar, a modification of the method of Brown, Morris and Millar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, **71**, 281).

The Fehling's solution was prepared according to the formula of Ling and Rendle (*Analyst*, 1908, **33**, 167) and had the following composition:—

Solution I—69.28 g. of copper sulphate pentahydrate per litre.

Solution II—346 g. of Rochelle salt
142 g. of caustic soda } per litre.

(In solution II, Brown and co-workers used only 130 g. of caustic soda).

The two solutions were kept separate and the required quantities of the mixture prepared just before use.

Procedure.—A definite amount of the reaction mixture containing not more than 100 milligrams of total sugar was pipetted out into an Erlenmeyer flask containing an amount of alkali just enough to neutralise the catalysing acid. This was then mixed with 50 c.c. of Fehling's solution, the mouth of the flask covered with a small beaker and heated in a water-bath at 99°-100° for exactly 12 minutes.

Brown, Morris and Millar recommend heating Fehling's solution only in boiling water first and then, after adding the sugar solution, heating the mixture in the bath for exactly 12 minutes. We have found, however, that when we use the Fehling's solution prepared to Ling's formula, quantitative results are obtained by heating the mixture for exactly 12 minutes in the water-bath.

The mixture after reaction was rapidly filtered through asbestos in a Gooch crucible, the entire cuprous oxide precipitate transferred to the crucible and well washed with distilled water, free from air and carbon dioxide. Next the asbestos mat with the cuprous oxide precipitate was transferred back to the Erlenmeyer flask. The crucible was then placed in a funnel over the flask and carefully rinsed first with 25 c.c. of a saturated solution of ferric alum in 25 p. c. sulphuric acid and then with 25 c.c. of 25 p. c. sulphuric acid, so that any

precipitate sticking to the sides of the crucible might get dissolved and the entire washings collected in the flask. A pinch of sodium carbonate was next added to the flask, the mouth of the flask closed with a rubber cork and the flask gently shaken. The entire precipitate dissolved in less than a minute. The mixture was then titrated against standard decinormal permanganate solution; (Brown and co-workers estimate the cuprous oxide gravimetrically). The amount of permanganate solution required for the titration is a measure of the amount of invert sugar present and the amount of unhydrolysed sucrose is computed by difference. The method gives accurate results, the error being generally between 0.40 and 0.50 per cent.

Results and Discussion.

The results of two characteristic experiments are given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I.

Temp. = 35°. Conc. of sucrose = 1.0 p.c.
Conc. of HCl = 0.10 N. 10 C.c.
taken for each analysis.

Time (min.).	Amount of sucrose in 10 c.c. (mg.).	0.434 k.
0	89.00	—
30	80.50	0.001453
60	72.67	0.001468
90	65.83	0.001455
120	59.50	0.001458
150	53.50	0.001466
210	43.67	0.001472
270	36.17	0.001449
330	29.50	0.001453
390	23.00	0.001471
∞	0.00	Mean 0.001460

TABLE II.

Temp. = 35°. Conc. of sucrose = 0.10 p.c. Conc. of HCl = 0.10 N.
50 C.c. taken for each analysis.

Time (min.).	Amount of sucrose in 50 c.c. (mg.).	0.434 k.
0	42.83	—
30	38.87	0.001420
60	35.17	0.001425
90	32.00	0.001407
120	29.17	0.001411
150	26.17	0.001426
210	21.67	0.001409
270	17.67	0.001424
390	12.00	0.001416
∞	0.00	Mean 0.001417

Table III contains data obtained with different concentrations of sucrose, at 35° and 45°, the concentration of hydrochloric acid being the same (0.10 %) in all the solutions.

TABLE III.

Conc. of sucrose (M).	0.434 k_{35}° .	0.434 k_{45}° .	$k_{45}^{\circ}/k_{35}^{\circ}$.
0.002924	0.001417	0.004969	3.506
0.007310	0.001430	0.005000	3.496
0.01462	0.001441	0.005058	3.510
0.00924	0.001460	0.005111	3.500
0.05848	0.001477	0.005171	3.501
0.03772	0.001478	0.005193	3.513
0.1462	0.001482	0.005203	3.511
0.2924	0.001522	0.005333	3.504
		Mean	3.505

Comparison of the values of the velocity constants with those obtained by the polarimetric method.—Moran and Lewis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1617) find for the velocity constant with a 10 per cent. sucrose solution and 0.10 N hydrochloric acid at 35° a value $k = 5.65 \times 10^{-5}$ (calculations made to the base e and seconds⁻¹). Under the same conditions we find from the results given in Table III that $k = 5.83 \times 10^{-5}$. By extrapolation, Lewis and Moran obtain for zero concentration sucrose $k = 5.00 \times 10^{-5}$, while in our experiment with 0.10 per cent. sucrose solution, we find $k = 5.432 \times 10^{-5}$. The agreement between the values of k in the case of 10 per cent. sucrose solution is quite satisfactory, while in the case of solutions, whose sucrose concentration is in the neighbourhood of zero, the difference is about 8 per cent. It may therefore be concluded that the chemical method gives almost the same results as the polarimetric method.

Variation of k with concentration of sucrose.—A glance at Table III shows that with increase in the concentration of sucrose from 0.10 per cent. to 10 per cent. at constant catalyst concentration, the velocity constant gradually, though slowly, increases at constant temperature. It has been shown by Moran and Lewis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1620) that the activity of the hydrogen ion in decinormal solutions of hydrochloric acid increases with increase in sucrose concentration and the activity of the hydrogen ion certainly exerts the major regulating effect on the velocity of hydrolysis. If k varies directly as the activity of the hydrogen ion, then $\frac{k_{10\%}}{k_{0.10\%}}$ must be equal to $\frac{a_{H^+10\%}}{a_{H^+0.10\%}}$ where $a_{H^+10\%}$ and $a_{H^+0.1\%}$ represent the activities of the hydrogen ions in 10 per cent. and 0.10 per cent. solutions of sucrose respectively. If we assume

that a 0.10 per cent. solution of sucrose approximates in its properties to pure water, according to Moran and Lewis (*loc. cit.*)

$\left(\frac{a_{\text{H}^+ 10\%}}{a_{\text{H}^+ \text{ pure water}}} \right)$ is equal to 1.192 while according to our experi-

ments $\frac{k_{10\%}}{k_{0.10\%}}$ is equal to 1.074. This means that the rate of

increase of velocity is not as great as the rate of increase of activity of the hydrogen ion.

Temperature coefficient of k.—Figures in the extreme right column of Table III indicate that $\frac{k_{45^\circ}}{k_{35^\circ}}$ is quite constant over the

entire range of concentrations of sucrose studied, the average value for this ratio being 3.505. This gives on calculation 24541 calories as the energy for the critical increment, while the results of Moran and Lewis (*loc. cit.*) lead to the value 26105 calories for the same.

Variation of k with acid concentration.—Table IV summarises the results at 35° obtained with different concentrations of hydrochloric acid. In all these experiments, the concentration of sucrose was the same (1 g. per 100 c.c.). In the third column of the table

are given values for the ratio $\frac{0.434 k \times 10^2}{C_{\text{HCl}}} = r$, in the fourth column

the activities of hydrogen ions in the different solutions and in the

fifth column values for the ratio $\frac{0.434 k \times 10^2}{a_{\text{H}^+}}$.

TABLE IV.

Conc. of HCl (mole/litre).	$0.434 k \times 10^2$.	r .	a_{H^+} .	$\frac{0.434 k}{a_{\text{H}^+}} \times 10^2$.
0.001	1.377	1.377	0.000993	1.386
0.002	2.758	1.379	0.001972	1.400
0.005	6.895	1.379	0.004835	1.426
0.008	11.050	1.381	—	—
0.010	13.850	1.385	0.00933	1.489
0.020	27.840	1.392	0.01850	1.508
0.050	70.750	1.415	0.04420	1.578
0.100	146.000	1.460	0.08660	1.683
0.200	304.000	1.520	0.1714	1.773
0.400	655.200	1.638	0.3572	1.834
0.600	1050.600	1.751	0.5748	1.828
0.800	1508.800	1.886	0.8336	1.809
1.000	2010.000	2.010	0.1410	1.761

These figures show that in very dilute solutions (up to about 0.01 N) of the acid, r remains almost constant and then it begins to increase with increased concentration of the acid. r plotted against the concentration of the acid (c as abscissae) gives a curve which is slightly concave downward (Fig. 1). This means

FIG. 1.

that the salt effect of the acid molecule is greater at lower than at higher concentrations.

The ratio $\frac{k}{C_{\text{HCl}}}$ is to be regarded as the molar velocity constant in this catalysis. If $\frac{k}{C_{\text{HCl}}} = V$, then $r = 0.434 V$. From the curve in Fig. 1 we get the following relation

$$0.434V = 1.376 \times 10^{-2} + 0.84 \times 10^{-2} \cdot C_{\text{HCl}},$$

for the molar velocity constant for concentrations of acid up to about 0.12N.

Activity of the hydrogen ion and the velocity constant.—Since the concentration of sugar in the above experiments is very small, we might assume that the influence of sucrose in these solutions on the activities of H^+ and water is negligible. The measurements of Harned (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1808) furnish us with data regarding the activity coefficients of H^+ in solutions of HCl of different concentrations at 25°. The activity coefficient of an ion does not vary very much over a small range of temperature like 10° and we might regard the activities of H^+ in different solutions at 35° to be the same as at 25°. The values given in Harned's paper refer to molal concentrations of hydrochloric acid. For our purposes we have calculated the corresponding values for molar concentrations from Harned's data and these are the values given in column of 4 Table IV.

It will be observed from the table that even in very dilute solutions of the acid the ratio $\frac{0.434 k}{a_{\text{H}^+}}$ very rapidly increases with increased concentration of the acid. If the activity of the catalysing ion is what tells in the reaction, we should have found the ratio $\frac{0.434 k}{a_{\text{H}^+}}$ constant at different concentrations of the acid, at least in very dilute solutions. It is to be particularly noted that the values for the ratio $\frac{0.434 k}{a_{\text{H}^+}}$ are always higher than $\frac{0.434 k}{C_{\text{HCl}}}$ at corresponding concentrations of the acid, except at the last two concentrations of the acid studied. This shows that the velocity constant increases much faster than is warranted by the increase in the thermodynamic concentration of hydrogen ion.

Effect of neutral salts.—Table V gives the results of velocity of measurements made to test the influence of neutral salts. In these experiments, the concentrations of sugar and hydrochloric acid were kept constant (1 g. of sucrose per 100 c.c. and 0.10 N-HCl) while the concentrations of the salts were varied. Experiments were carried out only with the chlorides of potassium, sodium and lithium.

TABLE V.

Salt Conc. (mole/litre).	0.434 $k \cdot 10^4$.		
	KCl.	NaCl.	LiCl.
0	14.60	14.60	14.60
0.10	15.30	15.30	15.40
0.20	15.70	15.88	16.27
0.50	17.00	17.30	18.10
1.00	19.59	20.91	22.30
2.00	27.23	29.12	33.50
3.00	37.35	43.30	49.83

Results given in Table V indicate that the effectiveness in increasing the velocity constant for the three salts investigated is in the following order—LiCl > NaCl > KCl.

Very recently Kautz and Robinson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1022) have made a study of the hydrolysis of sucrose with hydrochloric acid, in presence of alkali and alkaline earth chlorides at 25°. Their results were obtained with 20 per cent. sugar solutions. The concentrations of salts and hydrochloric acid employed by them were the same as in our experiments. Our experiments were of course carried out at 35°. In Table VI we have compared the ratios we obtain from our results $\frac{k \text{ (velocity constant in presence of salt)}}{k_0 \text{ (velocity constant only with 0.10N-HCl)}}$ with the corresponding ratios taken from Kautz and Robinson's paper. Figures given under the subscripts (K&S) and (K&R) refer to our and Kautz and Robinson's results respectively.

TABLE VI.

Salt conc. (mole/litre).	k/k_0		k/k_0		k/k_0	
	(K&R)	(K&S)	(K&R)	(K&S)	(K&R)	(K&S)
	KCl		NaCl		LiCl	
0.10	1.07	1.048	1.13	1.048	1.14	1.054
0.20	1.15	1.075	1.18	1.088	1.21	1.114
0.50	1.26	1.164	1.27	1.185	1.30	1.239
1.00	1.51	1.341	1.54	1.432	1.57	1.527
2.00	2.24	1.865	2.26	1.994	2.52	2.294
3.00	3.12	2.548	3.47	2.965	4.07	3.413

It will be observed that the ratios obtained by us are throughout lower (very much lower at higher concentrations of salts) than the corresponding ratios obtained by Kautz and Robinson. As pointed out above, their results were obtained with 20% sugar solutions. Since, in general, the activities of ions are much greater in sugar solutions than in pure water, assuming that our dilute sugar solutions approximate in behaviour to pure water, we can qualitatively explain the higher values obtained by Kautz and Robinson, as being due to the higher activities of hydrogen ions in the solutions employed by them.

It is worthwhile examining how far our results can be accounted for by the increased activity of hydrogen ions in salt solutions. Harned (*loc. cit.*) has determined by *E. M. F.* measurements the activity coefficients of hydrogen ion in decinormal solutions of hydrochloric acid in the presence of alkali chlorides at 25°. If we were to assume here again, that the activity coefficient of an ion at 35° does not differ much from its value at 25° in any given solution, we could utilise Harned's data for our present purpose. If the velocity constant of the reaction is strictly proportional to the activity of the hydrogen ion, we ought to get a constant value for the ratio $\frac{0.434 \cdot k}{a_{H^+}}$. These ratios in the different solutions together with the activities of hydrogen ions in those solutions are given in Table VII.

TABLE VII.

Salt conc. (M).	KCl		NaCl		LiCl	
	a_{H^+} .	$0.434k/a_{H^+}$.	a_{H^+} .	$0.434k/a_{H^+}$.	a_{H^+} .	$0.434k/a_{H^+}$.
0.0	0.0869	1.680				
0.10	0.0876	1.747	0.0897	1.706	0.0908	1.696
0.20	0.0884	1.776	0.0918	1.730	0.0945	1.722
0.50	0.0929	1.830	0.0989	1.749	0.1066	1.698
1.00	0.1018	1.925	0.1152	1.815	0.1362	1.638
2.00	0.1326	2.054	0.1681	1.733	0.2290	1.464
3.00	0.1785	2.093	0.2660	1.618	0.4100	1.215

It will be seen from Table VII, that the ratio $0.434k/a_{H^+}$ is in no case constant. In the case of potassium chloride, it gradually increases with increased concentration of salt. In the case of sodium chloride, it reaches a maximum at 1.0 *N* and then falls, while in case of lithium chloride solutions, the maximum is reached even at 0.20 *N* and then it begins to fall. The increase in velocity constant would therefore appear to be more subject to the specific influences of the different salts and cannot be attributed merely to the hydrogen ion activities in the salt solutions.

Schmid and Olsen (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 97, 124) proposed the following empirical relation between the molar concentration of the salt and the velocity constant, $k = k_0 e^{ac}$, where k_0 is the velocity constant in the absence of salt, c the concentration of the added salt and a a constant for any particular salt. Grube and Schmid (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 119, 19) have found this simple relationship to hold good also in the case of the acid hydrolysis of cyanamide. This expression can be written in the form $\log k = \log k_0 + a.c$.

We find plotting $\log (0.434 k)$ from our data against c , that very good straight lines are obtained in the case of all the three salts, as demanded by the above expression. For the three salts KCl, NaCl and LiCl, the characteristic constants have values 0.135, 0.1564 and 0.1767 respectively.

Considerations regarding the mechanism of the reaction.—Scatchard (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 2387) drew attention to the fact that previous workers, who tried to interpret data on the kinetics of sucrose hydrolysis, did not practically take into account

the role water played in the reaction. In his two papers on the mechanism of the inversion process in concentrated sucrose solutions (*loc. cit.*), he started with the assumption that n molecules of water take part in the reaction and introducing this factor into the kinetic expression, arrived at the equation

$$k = \frac{k_{\text{uni}}}{a_{\text{H}^+} \times a_w^n},$$

where k_{uni} stands for the usual unimolecular velocity constant, a_{H^+} , the activity of the hydrogen ion and a_w , the activity of water. Scatchard finds that when n is assigned a value of 6, the observed results could be quantitatively explained. We tried to apply this equation and see how far the data in Tables IV and V of this paper lend support to this mechanism. We calculated the activities of water in different HCl and salt solutions from the best available vapour pressure data and found that in no case could we get constant values for k in the above equation. With increased electrolyte concentration, we found that the value for the ratio $\frac{k_{\text{uni}}}{a_{\text{H}^+} \times a_w^6}$ gradually increased. We have therefore not given the results of these calculations here.

It is clear from what we have seen in previous sections of the paper, that the velocity of hydrolysis, even in very dilute solutions of sucrose, does not vary simply as the activity of the hydrion. It is now generally recognised that hydrogen ion in water exists not as mere proton but as the hydrated ion H_3O^+ (Brönsted, Acid and Basic Catalysis, Chemical Reviews, V. 1928. Chapters VI, VII and VIII.). It is possible that the hydrolysis is a mere bimolecular reaction taking place between the sucrose (S) and the oxonium ion, according to the scheme

According to this scheme, the expression for the reaction rate according to Brönsted's theory will be

$$h = k_1 \cdot C_s \cdot C_{\text{H}_3\text{O}^+} \cdot \frac{F_s \cdot F_{\text{H}_3\text{O}^+}}{F_x^+} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where F_s , $F_{H_3O^+}$ and F_x^+ stand for the activity coefficients of the sugar molecule, H_3O^+ ion and the critical collision complex respectively. In very dilute solutions, the activity coefficients of all univalent ions may be regarded as being equal and the activity coefficient of the nonelectrolyte sucrose molecule as being equal to unity, so that we should expect the above expression (1) to assume the simple classical form

$$h = k_1 \cdot C_s \cdot C_{H_3O^+}.$$

Since during the course of the reaction $C_{H_3O^+}$ remains constant,

$$h = k \cdot C_s,$$

where k is the unimolecular velocity constant, being equal to $k_1 \cdot C_{H_3O^+}$. It follows therefore

$$k_1 = k / C_{H_3O^+} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

We find actually from Table IV that this relationship holds good only for very dilute solution up to a concentration of hydrochloric acid 0.008 N.

It should however, be pointed out here that above conclusion can be arrived at for very dilute solutions, even if it be assumed, as has been done by Scatchard (*loc. cit.*), that water molecules also take a direct part in the reaction.

For more concentrated solutions, this relationship cannot be expected to hold good. $F_{H_3O^+}$ and F_x^+ should be expected to have different values, specific individual effects coming into prominence. If, however, the ratio $F_{H_3O^+}/F_x^+$ does not considerably deviate from unity, then also we should expect to get constant values for $F_{H_3O^+}$. But there is yet F_s , whose value ought to vary with increase in concentration of electrolytes. The variation of F_s with concentration of electrolytes is not exactly known and there is no way of determining F_x^+ at different ionic concentrations, so that these difficulties stand in the way of testing any hypothesis regarding the mechanism of this reaction in a quantitative way.

Summary.

A study of the hydrolysis of sucrose in presence of hydrochloric acid has been made under the following conditions:—

(1) With different concentrations of cane sugar in the range 0.002924M—0.2924M, keeping the concentration of hydrochloric acid constant (0.10N) at 35° and 45°.

(2) With different concentrations of hydrochloric acid in the range $0.001N-1.00N$, keeping the concentrations of cane sugar constant ($0.02924M$) at 35° .

(3) With different concentrations of the three neutral salts KCl , $NaCl$ and $LiCl$ in the range $0.10N-3.0N$, keeping the concentrations of sucrose ($0.02924 M$) and hydrochloric acid ($0.10 N$) constant at 35° .

It has been found that under the conditions specified in (1) with increase in sucrose concentration at constant temperature, the velocity constant gradually increases, but the rate of increase is not as great as the rate of increase of the activity of hydrogen ion in these solutions.

$k_{45^\circ}/k_{35^\circ}$ is quite constant over the entire range of concentrations of sucrose, having an average value 3.505 .

Under the conditions specified in (2), the ratio k/C_{acid} remains constant in dilute solutions up to a concentration of about $0.01N$ and then increases with increase in concentration of acid. The molar velocity constant V , in this catalysis, up to a concentration of about $0.12N$ has been found to be faithfully expressed by the equation

$$0.434V = 1.376 \times 10^{-2} + 0.84 \times 10^{-2}.C,$$

where C is the concentration of the acid.

The neutral salt effect in the reaction has been found to follow the simple empirical relation, $k = k_0 e^{ac}$, proposed by Schmid and Grube (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **119**, 19) and Schmid and Olsen (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **124**, 97). The characteristic constant (a) for the three salts KCl , $NaCl$ and $LiCl$ have been found to be equal to 0.135 , 0.1564 and 0.1767 respectively.

In the presence of salts, the increase in hydrogen ion activity does not account quantitatively for the increase in velocity of hydrolysis.

A few points regarding the mechanism of the hydrolysis have been briefly discussed.

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